

Predicted Elastic Constants of Transversely Isotropic Composites Containing Anisotropic Fibers

S. K. Datta¹⁾, H. M. Ledbetter²⁾, R. D. Kriz²⁾

1) Mechanical Engineering Department, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO 80309, U.S.A.

2) Fracture & Deformation Division, National Bureau of Standards, U.S. Department of Commerce, NBS-562, 325 Broadway, Boulder, CO 80303, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

By a wave-scattering method, we derive dispersion relationships for waves propagating perpendicular to continuous fibers that are oriented unidirectionally. In the long-wavelength limit one obtains relationships that predict the composite's effective static elastic constants. We compare these relationships with others derived by energy methods to obtain upper and lower bounds of the effective static moduli. We demonstrate this comparison graphically by plotting for graphite-epoxy the predicted composite constants over the full range of fiber volume fractions. We consider the fibers to be anisotropic, but transversely isotropic. Under special conditions, the energy-method upper and lower bounds compare identically with the results of this study. The static properties are, of course, special cases of the more general dispersion relationships. Graphs are given for nine elastic constants: axial and transverse Young's and shear moduli, bulk and plane-strain-bulk moduli, and three Poisson's ratios.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, both theory and observation of fiber-reinforced composites have advanced dramatically. Reviews of this subject include those on theory by Hashin [1], Sendekyj [2], and Walpole [3], and on experiment by Bert [4].

In practice, two types of fiber reinforcement occur: continuous-fiber and short-fiber (chopped-fiber). Most studies consider only the first type, which we consider here.

Most previous studies calculated overall (effective) static elastic constants or bounds of such constants. Some authors considered wave propagation in fiber-reinforced composites both for fibers in periodic arrays [5,6] and for fibers distributed randomly [7-9].

Random distributions of identical, long, parallel fibers form the subject of the present study. We focus on the propagation of plane longitudinal and shear waves propagating perpendicular to the fibers. We use a multiple scattering approach to obtain a dispersion relationship. This relationship governs both propagation velocity and frequency of the incident wave. We make three simplifying assumptions: (1) random and homogeneous fiber distribution, (2) Lax's

quasi-crystalline approximation, (3) wavelength long relative to fiber diameter. In this long-wavelength limit, one obtains effective static elastic constants that agree well with results obtained by other methods. For a graphite-epoxy composite, we consider fibers to be anisotropic, and we obtain elastic constants for all volume fractions.

2. FORMULATION

Consider a system of long circular cylindrical fibers embedded in an infinite matrix. We assume that the matrix is isotropic and homogeneous with Lamé constants λ and μ and mass density ρ and that the fibers are transversely isotropic with the axis of symmetry coincident with the fiber axis. We consider two problems. First, the propagation of shear waves moving perpendicular to the fibers. Here the particle motion is assumed to be parallel to the fibers. This SH-wave problem was considered in [7,9,10]. The second problem is that of propagation perpendicular to the fibers with the particle motion also perpendicular to the fibers. Details of the calculation for the first problem are given elsewhere [11]. The second problem can be analyzed similarly, but the algebra is much more complicated because of its vector nature.

2.1 SHEAR WAVE POLARIZED PARALLEL TO FIBER

Let the fibers be labeled 1, 2, ..., N and let (r_i, θ_i) be the polar coordinates of the center O of the i^{th} fiber. The z axis is the fiber axis. We assume that the fibers are identical in geometry and material properties, although for the following analysis this assumption is not necessary. In customary notation, the fiber elastic constants are denoted by C_{ij} ($i, j = 1-6$). Since the fibers are assumed transversely isotropic there are only five independent constants: C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{13} , C_{33} , and C_{44} .

For the problem considered in this section, the only elastic properties that enter the calculation are C_{44} and μ . Thus, the analysis follows closely that in [6] and is a special case of that in [8], which deals with elliptical-cross-section inclusions.

Let an SH wave given by

$$u_z^{(i)} = u_0 e^{i(\beta x - \gamma t)}, \quad \beta = \gamma/c_2, \quad c_2 = \sqrt{\mu/\rho} \quad (1)$$

be incident on the medium considered. Here u represents particle displacement, c_2 the shear-wave speed in the matrix, and γ the circular frequency. This incident wave will be scattered by N fibers. The dispersion equation is obtained [11] by equating the coefficients of X_0^+ and X_0^- to zero. For an arbitrary wavenumber the dispersion equation is rather complicated. We can approximate this equation by assuming that βa is small; this means the wavelength is long compared to the fiber diameter, $2a$. For small βa the following relationships can be obtained by equating the determinant of the coefficients to zero.

$$\left(\frac{\beta^*}{\beta}\right)^2 = [1 + C(\rho'/\rho - 1)] \frac{1 - C(m-1)/(m+1)}{1 + C(m-1)/(m+1)} \quad (2)$$

where $m = C_{44}/\mu$.

Defining the average density as

$$\rho^* = \rho[1 + C(\rho'/\rho - 1)] \quad (3)$$

and

$$\beta^* = \gamma/c_2^*, \quad c_2^* = \sqrt{\mu_{LT}/\rho^*} \quad (4)$$

where μ_{LT} is the effective axial shear modulus, one obtains:

$$\frac{\mu_{LT}}{\mu_m} = \frac{1 + C(m-1)/(m+1)}{1 - C(m-1)/(m+1)} \quad (5)$$

where m is the ratio of fiber and matrix shear moduli (μ_{LT}^i/μ_m) and C is the fiber volume fraction.

Equation (5) was obtained by Hashin and Rosen [10] using the composite cylinder assemblage (CCA) model. The expression for μ_{LT} obtained from (5) coincides with the lower (upper) bound when the fiber shear modulus, μ_{LT}^i , is larger (smaller) than the matrix shear modulus, μ_m .

2.2 LONGITUDINAL AND SHEAR WAVES POLARIZED PERPENDICULAR TO FIBER

Propagation of longitudinal and shear waves polarized transverse to the fibers was studied in [8] using the same approach as outlined above. It was shown that if βa and αa were assumed small then the dispersion relationships reduce to effective longitudinal and shear moduli transverse to the fibers. These are:

$$\frac{C_{11}}{\lambda_m + 2\mu_m} = \frac{1 - CP_2(1 - \beta^2/\alpha^2) - 2C^2P_0P_2}{(1 + CP_0)[1 + CP_2(1 + \beta^2/\alpha^2)]} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\mu_{TT}}{\mu_m} = 1 + \frac{2C(\mu_{TT}^i - \mu_m)(\lambda_m + 2\mu_m)}{2\mu_m(\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) + (1 - C)(\lambda_m + 3\mu_m)(\mu_{TT}^i - \mu_m)} \quad (7)$$

where

$$P_0 = -\frac{K_T^i - (\lambda_m + \mu_m)}{K_T^i + \mu_m}, \quad P_2 = -\frac{(\mu_{TT}^i - \mu_m)\mu_m}{\mu_{TT}^i(\lambda_m + 3\mu_m) + \mu_m(\lambda_m + \mu_m)}$$

$$\alpha^2 = \gamma^2/c_1^2, \quad c_1 = \sqrt{(\lambda_m + 2\mu_m)/\rho}$$

The effective transverse plane-strain bulk modulus, K_T , can be obtained from equations (6) and (7) as:

$$K_T = \lambda_m + \mu_m + (\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) \frac{C(K_T^i - \lambda_m - \mu_m)}{(1 - C)K_T^i + C\lambda_m + (1 + C)\mu_m} \quad (8)$$

where K_T^i is the transverse bulk fiber modulus and the matrix Lamé constants are λ_m and μ_m .

Equation (8) is the same as derived by Hashin and Rosen [12] using the CCA model. However, the CCA model was not used to derive an expression for the effective transverse shear modulus. Instead, using energy methods, bounds were derived for the transverse shear modulus. Expression (7) for μ_{TT} is identical to the lower (upper) bound given by Hashin and Rosen if μ_{TT}^i and K_T^i are larger (smaller) than μ_m and K_m , respectively, where $K_m = \lambda_m + \mu_m$ is the plane-strain bulk modulus of the matrix.

Knowing the expression for K_T one can predict the effective longitudinal Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio using relationships derived by Hill [13]. When both fiber and matrix phases are transversely isotropic, Hill shows that:

$$E_L = E_m(1 - C) + E_L' C + \frac{4C(1 - C)(v_{LT}' - v_m')^2}{(1 - C)/K_T' + C/K_m + 1/\mu_m} \quad (9)$$

$$v_{LT} = v_m(1 - C) + v_{LT}' C + \frac{C(1 - C)(v_{LT}' - v_m')(1/K_m - 1/K_T')}{(1 - C)/K_T' + C/K_m + 1/\mu_m} \quad (10)$$

where E_L' and v_{LT}' are the axial Young's modulus and axial Poisson's ratio of the fiber. The quantities subscripted with m designate the isotropic matrix properties.

For a unidirectional fibrous composite with transversely isotropic fibers, this completes the derivation of the five independent effective elastic properties: K_T , E_L , v_{LT} , μ_{TT} , μ_{LT} . Other elastic properties of physical significance can be calculated from the five effective properties. For instance, assuming isotropy in the transverse plane, the Poisson's ratio, v_{TT} , and the Young's modulus, E_T , can be calculated from the isotropic relationships. Thus,

$$E_T = \frac{4K_T\mu_{TT}}{K_T + \psi\mu_{TT}} \quad (11)$$

$$v_{TT} = \frac{K_T - \psi\mu_{TT}}{K_T + \psi\mu_{TT}} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\psi = 1 + \frac{4K_T v_{LT}^2}{E_L}$$

The remaining Poisson's ratio, v_{TL} , is calculated from the relationship obtained from the elastic-compliance symmetry condition:

$$v_{TL} = v_{LT} E_T/E_L \quad (13)$$

If the composite behaves transversely isotropic with the unique symmetry axis along x_3 , then the elastic-stiffness constants, C_{ij} , can be computed from

$$C_{11} = C_{22} = K_T + \mu_{TT} \quad (14)$$

$$C_{33} = E_L + 2v_{LT} C_{13} \quad (15)$$

$$C_{44} = C_{55} = \mu_{LT} \quad (16)$$

$$C_{12} = K_T - \mu_{TT} \quad (17)$$

$$C_{13} = C_{23} = 2v_{LT} K_T \quad (18)$$

$$C_{66} = (C_{11} - C_{12})/2 = \mu_{TT} \quad (19)$$

One can also calculate the bulk modulus, B, from

$$B = \frac{1}{9} \sum_{i,j=1,2,3} C_{ijij} = \{E_L + 4K_T[1 + \nu_{LT}(\nu_{LT} + 2)]\}/9 \quad (20)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of fiber volume fraction, C, on the predicted elastic constants can now be demonstrated given the isotropic matrix properties and the transversely isotropic fiber properties. The matrix and fiber elastic constants, listed in Table 1, were obtained from [14] where the fiber elastic properties were extrapolated from experiments of Dean and Turner [15] using the transversely isotropic relations derived by Hashin [1]. This extrapolation of fiber properties was done with the correction $\beta_2 = K_T^f / (K_T^f + 2\mu_{TT}^f)$ noted in [14]. The elastic properties (ν_{TT} , ν_{TL} , ν_{LT} , μ_{TT} , E_T , μ_{LT} , E_L , K_T , B) are shown in Figs. 1-4.

As noted above, the curves for K_T , μ_{TT} , and μ_{LT} coincide with the lower bounds of Hashin and Rosen [12] for the particular composite considered here. Of the nine elastic constants shown in Figs. 1-4, E_L best fits a simple rule of mixtures. (The correction term in (9) can be neglected.) Both B and ν_{LT} come close to fitting this rule; μ_{TT} , K_T , and E_T do not differ dramatically from linearity; but μ_{LT} , ν_{TT} , and ν_{TL} do so differ. Except for ν_{TT} and E_T all deviations from linearity are negative; that is, the curves are concave. The ν_{TT} curve is convex. The E_T curve is convex at low fiber fractions and concave at high. This reflects the abrupt rise of ν_{TT} at low fiber fractions combined with the slow, steady rise of μ_{TT} . For those constants that differ strongly from a rule of mixtures, both ν_{TT} and ν_{TL} are fiber-property dominated while μ_{LT} tends to be matrix-property dominated. The latter represents, of course, shear in the fiber direction.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Using a multiple-scattering approach, effective elastic constants of a graphite-fiber-reinforced epoxy composite were derived in this study. Graphite fibers were assumed to be anisotropic, but transversely isotropic. It was shown that the composite can be characterized as a transversely isotropic medium. All five elastic constants characterizing the composite were calculated. These elastic constants coincide with the lower bounds of those obtained by Hashin [1] using energy methods.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Composites studies of H.M.L. and R.D.K. are supported mainly by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Fusion Energy.

REFERENCES

1. Z. Hashin, Theory of Fiber-reinforced materials, NASA Report CR-1974 (1972).
2. G. P. Sendeckyj, Elastic behavior of composites, in Composite Materials, Volume 2, Academic (1974), pp. 45-83.
3. L. J. Walpole, Elastic behavior of composite materials: theoretical fundamentals, in Advances in Applied Mechanics, Volume 21, Academic (1981), pp. 169-242.
4. C. W. Bert, Experimental characterization of composites, in Composite Materials, Volume 8, Academic (1975), pp. 73-133.
5. J. D. Achenbach, Generalized continuum theories for directionally reinforced solids, Arch. Mech. 28, 257-278 (1976).

6. M. Hlavacek, A continuum theory of fiber-reinforced composites, *Int. J. Solids Structures* 9, 1075-1085 (1973).
7. S. K. Bose and A. K. Mal, Longitudinal shear waves in a fiber-reinforced composite, *Int. J. Solids Structures* 9, 1075-1085 (1973).
8. S. K. Bose and A. K. Mal, Elastic waves in a fiber-reinforced composite, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 22, 217-229 (1974).
9. S. K. Datta, Propagation of SH-waves through a fiber-reinforced composite -- elliptic cylindrical fibers, *J. Appl. Mech.* 42, 165-175 (1975).
10. S. K. Datta, Scattering by a random distribution of inclusions and effective elastic properties, in *Continuum Model of Discrete Systems, Solid Mechanics Study Series No. 12*, University of Waterloo Press (1978), pp. 111-127.
11. S. K. Datta, H. M. Ledbetter, R. D. Kriz, to be published.
12. Z. Hashin and B. W. Rosen, The elastic moduli of fiber-reinforced materials, *J. Appl. Mech.* 31, 223-232 (1964).
13. R. Hill, Theory of mechanical properties of fibre strengthened materials: I. elastic behaviour, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 12, 199-212 (1964).
14. R. D. Kriz and W. W. Stinchcomb, Elastic moduli of transversely isotropic graphite fibers and their composites, *J. Exper. Mech.* 19, 41-49 (1979).
15. G. D. Dean and P. Turner, The elastic properties of carbon fibers and their composites, *Composites* 4, 174-180 (1973).

Table 1. Matrix and fiber elastic constants, ref [14].

	E (GPa)	G (GPa)	ν
Epoxy	5.35	1.95	0.353
Graphite fiber (L)	232.0	24.0	0.290
Graphite fiber (T)	15.0	5.02	0.490

Figs. 1-4. Predicted elastic constants versus fiber volume fraction for graphite-epoxy composites.

